

METHODS OF DEVELOPING THE LEVELS OF PHYSICAL TRAINING OF FREESTYLE WRESTLING GIRLS

O‘zbekiston Davlat jismoniy tarbiya va sport universiteti,
Xalqaro kurash turlari nazariyasi va uslubiyati kafedrası o‘qituvchilari
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Annotation

Our national struggle is developing widely in many countries of the world. At present, the development of new training methods in order for Uzbek wrestlers to raise the flag of our country at the world arenas is one of the important issues. Therefore, we have used special method of development of physical qualities of wrestlers and presented results in this article.

Keywords: physical attributes, physical preparation, technical preparation, tactical preparation, special physical preparation.

ERKIN KUSHUCH QIZLARNING JISMONIY TARBIYA DARAJALARINI RIVOJLANTIRISH USULLARI.

Annotation

Milliy kurashimiz dunyoning ko‘plab mamlakatlarida keng rivojlanmoqda. Ayni paytda o‘zbek polvonlarining jahon arenalarida Vatanimiz bayrog‘ini baland ko‘tarishi uchun yangi tayyorgarlik uslublarini ishlab chiqish dolzarb masalalardan biridir. Shuning uchun biz ushbu maqolada kurashchilarning jismoniy sifatlarini rivojlantirishning maxsus usulidan foydalandik va natijalarni taqdim etdik.

Kalit so'zlar: jismoniy sifatlar, jismoniy tayyorgarlik, texnik tayyorgarlik, taktik tayyorgarlik, maxsus jismoniy tayyorgarlik.

Relevance: It is a great pleasure for the girls to be in the country while the number of people interested in sports is increasing. In this regard, the number of freestyle wrestlers is growing, but it is clear that new training methods are not enough in these arenas so that we can compete with other nations equally with their athletes. It is clear that some of the physical qualities of our freestyle wrestlers were insufficiently developed during the technical competitions.

Nowadays, the development of new methods of training for the Uzbek women's freestyle wrestlers to uplift the country's flag remains one of the pressing issues. while the Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On the Establishment of the Fund for the Development of Children's Sports of Uzbekistan" is aimed at the development of modern forms of physical and spiritual education of children. the development of methods, the formation of sports skills in children according to gender and age "(1) and also the Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On Measures for Further Development of Physical Training and Mass Sports" dated June 3, 2017, PD 3031. (2)

Research Purpose: Developing methods of improving their physical qualities so that they can win our freestyle wrestling championships in future competitions.

Object of research: The training process for free-wrestling girls.

The subject of the research: The physical qualities of 13-15 years old freestyle wrestlers.

Physical training of freestyle wrestlers is one of the most important components of sports training and is a process aimed at enhancing physical qualities - strength, endurance, flexibility, swiftness and speed.

The main objectives of physical training are:

- The level of athletes' health and their functional capacities in different organisms.

- Development of physical qualities in the physical qualities that conform to the peculiarities of the sport combat.

Physical training is divided into general, auxiliary and special training (3)

Physical training is interrelated with each other.

Failure to pay enough attention to any kind of physical training in the course of the event will ultimately hinder the growth of your athletic skills. Therefore, it is important to adhere to the optimal proportion of the types of physical training provided in the training process. (4)

The results of experiments and their discussion: According to preliminary findings, it was found out that, during the training sessions of the wrestling girls, especially in the early stages of the training, the development of physical qualities was one of the most important tasks. The experiment is aimed at raising girls up to 30% within the scope of the hours allocated for the development of special physical qualities in the training process.

A comparative analysis was made between a survey group of 15 female and 15 adult members of the freestyle wrestling team from 13 to 15 years of age to test for the correctness of the assumptions. At the beginning of the experiment, there were no statistically significant differences in the majority of the surveyed and tested women in the tested readiness of the freestyle wrestling girls.

At the beginning of the study, we developed a test test consisting of the collection of physical attributes and techniques to determine the level of physical development of the freestyle wrestlers and the level of their development. According to him, these tasks were not used to the health of the freestyle wrestlers and they were used with less difficult exercises.

Testing Tests:

- 1-Short distance run (30 meters)
- 2-bridge walk (up to 10 meters)
- 3-leap forward (meter)
- 4- Climbing to a 3 meter long rope
- 5 to 5 times to break down before a foot (time)
- 6-5 breaking through the foot of the foot (time)
- 7 to 5 seated over the shoulder
- 8 to 5 times to break down two legs (time)

The study lasted 2 months, and at the end of the study, we received a control test that was tested in both groups, and there was a distinction between them. Changes in physical and technical methods of wrestling girls can be seen in Figure 1.

Figure 1 shows a change in physical attitudes and technical readiness of the fighters.

Summary.

1- The development of technical skills of the freestyle wrestlers depends on a coach in many respects, and the coach should be able to see the flaws of the athlete in the performance of technical means and eliminate these shortcomings.

2- The trainer should be aware of not only the injury but also the correct distribution of the load - this, in turn, should be aware of the importance of future competition and competition tactics. That's why we always adhere to the coach's instructions.

3- A trainer should focus on the free qualities of freestyle wrestlers who are not only satisfied with their physical characteristics but also their inner qualities.

4- Freestyle wrestlers have good physical qualities, but they are not able to learn a variety of methods and apply them in competition.

5- Techniques given to them for the rapid preparation of the 1st female wrestlers were very slow and difficult. During the competition, they were unable to access the methods they learned. The 2-way-wrestler, however, has learned less technical techniques, but these methods have brought them victories in the competition.

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